

INFLUENCE OF LAGER BEER BILLBOARD ADVERTISING ON ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS LAGER BEER CONSUMPTION IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract

In spite of the regulation of alcohol advertising, distribution and consumption, billboard advertising of lager beer brands has become pervasive in South-East, Nigeria. This study examined Influence of Lager Beer Billboard Advertising on Attitude and Behaviour towards Lager Beer Consumption in South East Nigeria. The Explanatory Mixed Method Design was adopted for the study. The population of study was (24, 221, 021.) people. A sample size of six hundred (600.) was drawn from the population. Questionnaire was used to generate quantitative data. Major findings showed that 99% of the respondents were aware that different brands of lager beer exist and could identify them. Flowing from the above, 25.7% of the respondents have high knowledge of different brands of lager beer was influenced by exposure to lager beer billboard advertising', while, the knowledge of the majority (41.1%) was influenced to a moderate extent. The results indicated a very high exposure to lager beer billboards in South-East Nigeria. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended among others, that; owing to the harmful effects of alcohol and the high rate of its consumption among the audience, the researcher recommends a ban on lager beer and other alcoholic substances advertising. Definitely, this will not stop the consumption of alcohol, but, it can limit the rate at which people are introduced to alcohol. Warning signs on lager beer billboards should be bold and occupy a prominent position for it to command attention. This is because while the majority of the respondents acknowledged their attention to the graphics, message, slogans and icons/celebrities, a significant number of them failed to pay attention to the warnings by the Federal Ministry of Health. Since lager beer consumption is rated +18, it's suggested that the location of lager beer billboards should be prohibited in areas predominantly occupied by children and adolescents under the age of 18. The findings show that the use of celebrities and high-quality graphics received more attention on lager beer billboards than the text/message. Hence, pictures of celebrities accompanied with the brand, should play a prominent role in billboard advertising, especially, as research has shown that people may patronize a product based on the celebrity that endorsed it.

Keywords: Influence, Lager Beer, Billboard Advertising, Attitude, Behaviour, Lager Beer Consumption

Introduction

Lager beer advertising is one issue that is approached with great interest by scholars in Nigeria because of its controversial nature. The controversy bothers on whether or not alcohol should be

consumed and or whether its sale or consumption should be encouraged. Lager beer is an alcoholic beverage with a psychoactive content capable of causing harm to users. NAFDAC (2019, p. 6), describes it as “an alcoholic beverage resulting from fermentation of yeast culture of an extract derived from cereals, with or without malt, with or without adjuncts, with or without enzymes, with or without hops in potable water”. Zewdie (2018, p.13) argues that “beer is a universal product and almost all societies in the world produce beer in one form or another, whether such is at the industrial or the home level”. Beer is the world's most widely consumed alcoholic beverage. It is also the most popular drink after water and tea. Some people believe that it is the oldest fermented beverage (Arnold, 2005; Zewdie, 2018).

WHO (2014, p. Xiii) notes that “harmful use of alcohol causes a large disease, social and economic burden in societies”. Added to this, is the propriety or not of advertising alcoholic drinks in a religiously diverse environment where drinking of alcohol is prohibited for some religions and neighborhoods. Globally, alcoholic production, distribution and consumption is viewed with a great concern. Comparatively, the cost of producing alcohol weighs higher than the benefits or values to the society. Negussie and Berhane (2012, p. 216), explain that “excessive alcohol consumption was responsible for 1.8 and 2.5 million deaths worldwide, in the years 2004 and 2011, respectively. It was implicated in over 60 diseases, accidents and injuries and a contributing cause in 200 others.

In Nigeria, consumption of lager beer cuts across gender, age, occupation and social status. It can be taken at home, bar, café, or in any physical location. Except for underage persons, consumption of lager beer is not prohibited, nor considered socially unacceptable except when taken in excess.

The value of advertising to businesses is observed in the ability to enhance the visibility of products and organizations; while for the consumers, it provides product information necessary for informed market decisions. Radio, television, print media, and outdoor media are the major platforms through which the advertising process is accomplished. Of all these, billboard (outdoor) advertising favours the lager beer industry because of the unique attribute of immovability which allows it to focus attention on those who live, work or move within the coverage of the advertisement. Iveson (2011, p.151-174) agrees that “consumers spend a great amount of time each week in the car, and billboards are there to catch their attention whether they are on the freeway or alongside the main road”. Pedestrians and other road users get exposed to the billboards too. There is also the possibility of seeing the same billboard more than once a day in various locations (Adsource Outdoor, n.d; cited in Iveson, 2011).

For the purpose of conceptual clarification, a billboard is a stationary outdoor visual platform upon which advertising or public service announcements are placed. The description includes all elevated signs and signs that are attached on top of roofs and sides of buildings, but, excludes advertisements on the sides and tails of buses, handbills, highway department signs, banners, posters, advertisements painted on the body of buildings, and bus shelter advertisements (Luke, Esmundo & Bloom, 2000). For an advertisement on a billboard to add to the success of a product, it has to be planned in such a manner conforms to the five phases of the AIDCA model. That is, it must grab attention; pick audience interest on the product; stimulate desire; develop conviction within your prospects, and finally, inspire them to take action. The AIDCA model implies that the billboard should inject memorable and believable messages that will trigger consumers to act in a certain way (Brierley, 2002, cited in Ugonna, Okolo, Obikeze, Ohanagorom, Nwodo, & Oranusi, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

Globally, outdoor advertising of beer and other alcoholic beverages using billboards is viewed with concern because of the harmful effects of alcohol on health and other socio-economic consequences. Despite the regulation of alcohol advertising, distribution and consumption, billboard advertising of lager beer brands has become pervasive in South-East, Nigeria.

These lager beer billboards appear in different sizes and dimensions and with captivating messages or images that are presumably capable of catching the attention of passers-by. Its impact is predicated on

the strength of placement in an area with a high population concentration and multiple exposures to one image over a long period of time. Statistics show that on average, medium-sized billboards receive 10,000 to 20,000 views per location per day (Blueline Media, cited in, Thomas, 2015).

Scholars like Dumbili (2015a), Dumbili and Williams (2016b), and, Anderson, de Bruijn, Angus, Gordon, and Hastings (2009) have examined the impact of exposure to such media advertisement on inclination and motivation to purchase and or to consume alcohol. However, none of these studies targeted billboard advertising of lager beer nor focused on South-East, Nigeria, where consumption of alcohol is considered part of the social life (Lasebikan, Ayinde, Odunleye, Adeyefa, Adepoju, & Fakunle 2018; (Ibanga, Adetula, Dagona, Karick, & Ojiji, 2005). In view of this, the researchers seek to examine the extent exposure to lager beer billboard advertising influences attitude and behaviour towards lager beer consumption in South-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the extent of exposure to lager beer billboard advertisements among South-East residents.
2. To examine the South-East residents' perception of billboard advertisement of lager beer.
3. To interrogate the influence of lager beer billboard advertising on South-East residents' behaviour towards lager beer consumption.

Literature Review

Billboard Advertising

Advertising is simply the process of creating awareness about the existence of goods and services to a target audience. Advertising is defined as any non-personal communication means of ideas or products by using mass communications media such as television, newspapers, magazines, cinema, radio etc. and is implemented through a specific sponsor, who paid to influence consumer behaviour. Advertising is a form of non-personal method of communicating information which is usually paid for by a sponsor through various media. The focal point of these definitions is that advertising is a persuasive communication, because it tries to influence an audience to take to the sponsor's point of view and also take some appropriate actions towards an object (idea, product or service) of advertisement. "An advertisement is defined by the Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON) as a 'communication in the media paid for by an identifiable sponsor and directed at a target audience with the aim of transferring information about a product, service, idea or cause'" (Ukaegbu, 2013; cited in Ugonna, Okolo, Obikeze, Ohanagorom, Nwodo & Oranusi, 2017).

Billboards is a form of outdoor advertising and for a billboard to contribute to the success of a product, it has to be designed so that the customer passes through the five phases of the AIDCA theory, with all being equally important. The AIDCA theory implies that the billboard should inject memorable and believable messages that will trigger consumers to act in a certain way (Brierley, 2002 in Ugnna et al, 2017). Billboard is usually targeted at passers-by, drivers, those in moving vehicle and pedestrian traffic. They are characterized by attractive models' images and catchy slogans that attract attention.

The importance of billboard includes: high visual impact, low cost, high product visibility, high frequency, and immediate message delivery. One of the most effective ways to strengthen your company's brand recognition is billboard advertising because if placed in the right location, billboard advertising can increase traffic to your business, familiarize customers with your brand/product/service, and attract new customers who make impulse buying". Anna (2006) in Edegoh, *et al* (2013) affirms that "billboards are here to help us and be tangible reminder of what we have become and what we have achieved. Not only do they improve the visual quality of the area

where they are placed, they also serve as beautiful reminders of our past and the future”. Billboard has the potential to capture the attention of the audience on the go”.

Beer and Other Alcoholic Beverages Advertising on Billboards: A Review of Exposure and Perceptions

The leading breweries in Nigeria are Nigerian Breweries plc. and Guinness Nigeria (De Bruijn, 2011). Both breweries have their own company’s alcohol advertising codes which are endorsed by the breweries in Nigeria. The two largest breweries represent not only the most consumed brands but certainly the most advertised brands in Nigeria such as: *Star, Gulder, Guinness (Extra Stout), Harp, and Champion*.

The volume and content of advertising of alcoholic beverages contribute directly to the size of alcohol problems. Research conducted in the United States and Europe shows that alcohol advertising and promotion increase alcohol use, especially among new consumers (De Bruijn, 2011). Alcoholic beverage advertisements target the youthful population in society with the goal to disseminate information about their products, promote brand image, influence purchase and consumption decisions (Etokakpan & Sodeinde, 2021). Alcohol consumption and alcohol industry activities are rising throughout the African continent. Alcohol marketing is an important tool for the industry to create a favourable image around the product and to increase sales. Alcoholic beverage advertisers also aim to create a positive perception, affect attitude and change behaviours that would be favourable to the advertised brands. However, it has been observed that beer advertisements, are usually directly targeted at young men and not women and this can be seen in the contents, messages and appeals used in these advertisements (Lasebikan, 2016 cited in Etokakpan & Sodeinde, 2021).

Exposure to Beer Billboard Advertisements

The knowledge of a product is viewed as an identity that serves to build loyalty over time and persuade individuals, with the brands being used to consciously talk about the product. Customers’ knowledge of brand products has become an inevitable part of modern culture and global society, the most powerful tool in marketing products in the 21st century. The knowledge of a brand shows the ability of potential customers to recognize and to remember that a certain brand offers a certain level of satisfaction (Hartnett, Romaniuk & Kennedy, 2016). In this age of the internet, consumers gather most of the information about products and services through online channels and are likely to recall brands from their memory, in addition to seeing the advertisements in hard copies of newspapers, posters, magazines or billboards.

Dumbili and Williams (2016b) cited in Etokakpan and Sodeinde (2021), conducted a study on awareness of alcohol advertisements and perceived influence on alcohol consumption through an in-depth interview among male and female undergraduates (aged 19-23 years) from a South-Eastern Nigerian university. Findings revealed that there was a high level of awareness of alcohol advertisements among the students to the extent that they identified brand names of advertising messages that they have seen on television, and outdoor advertisements during football games, movies, news hours, on and around the campus. These advertisements influenced the students to consume alcohol, especially male students. Students exposed to alcohol advertisements demonstrated sophisticated levels of awareness of alcohol advertisements, to the extent that they named specific bars, restaurants and other sites where they had seen alcohol advertisements regularly; hence, the knowledge of a product is an important element to measuring consumers’ attitude, familiarity and acceptance of the product.

Attitude towards Alcohol Advertisements

In a competitive advertising market, every audience cannot react to messages about products in the same manner due to a variety of channels of communication and differences in the demographic factors of the potential consumers. In this way, Soo & Chia (2007) cited in Etokakpan and Sodeinde (2021) demonstrated that there can be differences between attitudes toward products which could be negative or positive. An attitude is regarded as positive where a product offers a favourable response

from the consumer and usually increases demand, acceptance, and the desire for the product. On the other side, a negative attitude from the consumer on a particular product entails a cognitive dissonance and invariably causes withdrawal from the use of the product (Etokakpan & Sodeinde, 2021).

This means that for a product to sustain a position in the market, it requires the product to pass the test of the positive or negative attitude of the consumers. Consequently, advertisers understudy the changing attitude of consumers to continually remain relevant and enjoy favourable consumer dispositions on their different products (Adebiyi & Bada, 2014). Where an advertiser of a beer product tends to observe that its brand does not have a favourable disposition of consumers it quickly engages in the repositioning of the product with innovations to meet the expectations of consumers. Since the attitude of product consumers has never been constant, beer advertisers are expected to conduct a periodic review of product performance (Etokakpan & Sodeinde, 2021).

An attempt to understand how people perceive alcohol advertisements is to measure what consumers see in advertisements, including, but not limited to models, settings, messages, colours, music, narratives and representations. Some beer consumers tend to see advertisements as attractive due to the 'happiness' displayed in the picture and the fine clothes worn by the women in the advertisements. The main themes expressed in connection with beer advertisements are fun, joy, happiness, success, prestige, friendship and togetherness. In another angle, the perceptions of consumers to beer advertisements are based on thoughts from the message of the advertisements. The messages express clear purposes (Chen, *et al.*, 2005). The advertisements tell the people to drink, make people drink; and increase sales (Dumbili, 2016b). The audience members form a perception about products and their advertisements before they purchase or consume such products. The views and interpretation of advertisements by the consumers are due to individual differences. These differences determine their perception and reaction

Empirical Review of Alcohol Consumption and Billboard Advertising

Etokakpan and Sodeinde (2021) examined the knowledge, attitude and perception of beer advertisements among female corps members in Lagos State, Nigeria. This paper was hinged on social judgment, stimulus-response and perception theories. Employing the survey research design, a sample size of 400 Batch A, 2020 female National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) members in Lagos State was used for the study. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select respondents and beer advertisements. Findings revealed that female corps members in Lagos State were knowledgeable about beer advertisements, had a negative attitude and a negative perception about beer advertisements. It was recommended that beer advertisers should create adverts that also target the female population. Women should not also be represented in stereotypical ways as female audiences currently have a negative attitude and perception of these representations in current advertisements. The Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria should also review the code of practice to include restrictions against the portrayal and promotion of female stereotypes. This study failed did not study the influence of lager beer advertising on its audience.

Schooler and Basil (1989) conducted a study titled "alcohol and cigarette advertising on billboards: targeting with social cues". The objective was to examine whether billboard advertising of tobacco and alcohol products is differentially targeted toward White, Asian, and Hispanic neighbourhoods. The content analysis method was adopted for the study and it analyzed 901 billboards in neighbourhood commercial districts in San Francisco, California, giving particular attention to tobacco and alcohol billboards. Neighbourhood census data were merged with billboard data to address this question. The study also proposes a theoretical model to explain how this medium is effective. The social aspects of drinking and smoking are posited to be important positive product attributes. The study suggests that the modelling of social cues can serve to motivate product use, disinhibit behavioural restraints, and reinforce existing habits (Schooler & Basil, 1989).

The data suggest that: (1) across all billboard advertising of products and services, tobacco (11%) and alcohol (17%) products were the most heavily advertised; Black and Hispanic neighbourhoods had more tobacco and alcohol billboards than White or Asian neighbourhoods; Black neighbourhoods had the highest per capita rate of billboard advertising; and there were more Black models per 1,000 Black people than there were ethnic models for other ethnic groups. Furthermore, the analyses of the content of the billboards revealed that alcohol and cigarette advertisements, use social modelling cues such as anticipated rewards, attractive models, and similarity. It was recommended that this understanding of social influence and modelling on billboards should provide health professionals with information to counter the strategies of tobacco and alcohol advertisers. This study analyzed the content of the billboards but failed to analyze the influence on the audience (Schooler & Basil, 1989).

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Reasoned Action was developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1975 as an improvement on the information integration theory, after trying to determine the differences between attitude and behaviour (Lumen Learning, n.d.). Customers act on behaviours that they believe will create or receive a particular outcome, and this explains the relationship between attitude and behaviour of humans. Individual's intention to engage in behaviour at a specific time and place. It is to predict how individuals will behave based on their pre-existing attitudes and behavioural intentions (Lumen Learning, n.d.). This theory emphasizes the fact that the attitude of the audience will determine how they would react to messages disseminated on media channels. Relating this theory to this study, it shows that decision to patronize an advertised lager beer brand is not solely dependent on exposure to the advertisement or the advertised brand, but involves a well thought out process based on perceived benefits or otherwise of the intended action (patronage) and other exogenous considerations.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey. The justification for the choice of survey is that the research method involves examining attitude, motivations, inclinations, behaviours and other observable human practices. The projected population of the study is 5,150,115 using an annual growth rate of 3.2% as recommended by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The Creative Research Systems Online Sample Size Calculator was used to arrive at the sample size of 600. The multi-stage sampling procedure was used to carry out the study. The researchers made use of the questionnaire for the collection of data for the study. The measuring instruments were face validated by two researchers in the Departments of Mass Communication, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. In order to ascertain the reliability of the measuring instrument, the researchers conducted a pilot study using twenty-four copies of the approved questionnaire on some respondents in four selected study areas. The quantitative data was collated, presented and analyzed using tables, charts and simple percentages.

Discussion of Results/Findings

Research Question One: What is the South-East residents' level of exposure to lager beer advertisements on billboards?

The essence of this research question was to ascertain the level of exposure to lager beer advertisements on billboards. The preliminary questions show that a significant majority of the respondents know that lager beer is a kind of alcoholic beverage, and also are aware that lager beer is advertised on billboards. Also, 99.3% of the respondents have seen a lager beer billboard advertisement before. This finding is a confirmation of the statement by Thomas (2015, p. 2), that, "on average, medium-sized billboards receive 10,000 to 20,000 views per location per day". Bearing in mind that exposure is the primary aim of every advertising campaign, the high penetration of lager beer billboards is implicative of a successful campaign for the different lager beer brands in South-East, Nigeria. It only remains to measure the effectiveness of such concentration and exposure to knowledge and patronage of different lager beer brands, since, AIDA model suggests that for an

advertisement, it has grab attention; pick audience interest on the product; stimulate desire; develop conviction within your prospects, and finally, inspire them to take action.

Research Question Two: What is the South-East residents' perception of billboard advertisement of lager beer?

Here, our findings, indicate that 46.2% of the respondents had a positive perception or attitude towards billboard advertisement of lager beer, while, 33.6% were negatively disposed to it. However, 20.2% were neutral. In a similar study, Aiken, Lam, Gilmore, Burns, Chikritzhs, Lenton, Lloyd, Lubman, Ogeil, and Allsop (2018) found that positive perception of advertisements was associated with increased intention to use and to purchase advertised products (n=68).

Research Question Three: To what extent does lager beer billboard advertising influence behaviour of South-East residents towards lager beer consumption?

The majority (32.2%) of the respondents reveal that exposure to lager beer billboard positively affected their attitude towards lager beer consumption to a moderate extent, while the attitude of another 25.5% positively influenced to a large extent. However, 0.5% of the respondents, to a large extent, was influenced negatively towards alcohol consumption. Also, a rating scheme used to measure opinions on the "extent lager beer billboard advertising influence behaviour towards lager beer consumption reveals that exposure to the billboards influenced the 22.1% of respondents' behaviour towards lager beer consumption to a high extent; 33.7% of the respondents' behaviour to a moderate extent, and 21.7% to a little. Dumbili and Williams's (2016) findings also point to the ways in which awareness of advertisements is perceived to influence the participants' alcohol consumption. While none of the females indicated that alcohol advertisements affected their drinking, some of the male participants noted that they were 'enticed' by alcohol advertisements, and thus they decided to try a new brand.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusion reached, the researcher recommends thus:

1. Owing to the harmful effects of alcohol and the high rate of its consumption among the audience, the researcher recommends a ban on lager beer and other alcoholic substances advertising. Definitely, this will not stop the consumption of alcohol, but, it can limit the rate at which people are introduced to alcohol.
2. Warning signs on lager beer billboards should be bold and occupy a prominent position for it to command attention. This is because while majority of the respondents acknowledged their attention to the graphics, message, slogan and icons/celebrities, a significant number of them failed to pay attention to the warnings by the Federal Ministry of Health.
3. Since lager beer consumption is rated +18, it's suggested that the location of lager beer billboards should be prohibited in areas predominantly occupied by children and adolescents under the age of 18.

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